

CHARACTERISTICS OF MEDIA CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF UNIVERSAL AND NATIONAL MEDIA SPACE (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN)

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Annotation: This article discusses the traditional types of media centers, modern types, systems and institutions that are part of socio-cultural reality, the formation and functioning of media centers in Karakalpakstan in a certain universal and national cultural space, as well as the formation and improvement of this space.

Key words: institution, reality, dialectical reality, common interests, laws of development, historical and cultural development, political experiences, constitutional ideals, ethno-values, geographical areas, media centers, modern technology tools.

Both traditional and modern types of media centers are systems and institutions that are part of socio-cultural reality. It is known that the manifestation of socio-cultural reality in the universal and national space is an axiom. Therefore, the media centers in Karakalpakstan are formed and operate in a certain universal and national cultural space and serve to form and improve this space. This dialectical relationship is in accordance with the principle of the subject within the subject, the Republic within the Republic. No matter what institution or reality in the Republic of Karakalpakstan we think about, we should proceed from this dialectical reality, not from the point of view of pitting them against each other or discriminating the other, but from the point of view of the commonality of interests, the generality of the laws of development. There are general laws of our democratic development that are consistent with the principles of universality, including: 1) unity of our historical and cultural development; 2) the exactness of our socio-political experiences and constitutional ideals, 3) the commonality of our ethno-values; 4) integrity of our geographical areas and our state; 5) our equality; 6) such as the proximity of social democratic norms that our media spaces follow and respect.

There is no need to justify the unity of the historical and cultural development of the Karakalpak and Uzbek peoples, because all historical and ethnological studies confirm the accuracy of their ethnogenesis[1]. This identity was formed in the process of historical and cultural development, as a result of which the two ethnic groups came closer to each other and communal aspects appeared. For example, Karakalpak and Uzbek understand each other without a translator, can read each other's writings and information, and easily accept symbolic signs in their information. Media centers not only rely on the unity formed in the processes of historical and cultural development, but serve to strengthen it according to the requirements of the time. For the effective operation of media centers, it is enough to rely on this historical-cultural experience and promote it with modern technology. For example, in the systems of general education, secondary special education and higher education conducted in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, almost no universal or national obstacles were encountered in the transition to the use of information technologies in educational processes.

The introduction of information and communication tools, called "modern pedtechnology", which began in the early ears of independence, was perceived as an update. Laws "On Education" (1997), "On National Personnel Training Program" (1997), "On Information" (2004) adopted by our state, strengthening the material and technical base of the President's Higher Education Institutions and fundamentally improving the quality of training highly qualified specialists on measures" (2011) and in many Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers "On the program for the development of computerization and information technologies in 2002-2010" (2002), arming the national education system with modern information education tools, which are already used abroad as indicators of universal cultural development introduction of interactive, distance and digital education methods is put on the agenda as strategic tasks. They recognized the possibilities of modern information and communication tools to create a universal media space and set an important goal that they would lead to wide integration in the field of education. As a result, modules and standards such as Forms, Materials, Messenger, Chat, Exercises, Group Work, Student tracking, IMS, SCORM on the Moodle platform appeared in the education and personnel training system. For example, in the Karakalpak State University named after Berdak, in the mid-1990s, separate courses and lessons were organized on the use of computer technology and the formation of students' skills in using information media, along with the technology of introducing modern ped-technologies. Preparation of electronic copies of important articles in the literature, textbooks and training manuals, newspapers and magazines, Bulletins in the university library has been started[2]. However, it is not observed that there has been a significant change in this regard due to the fact that the material and technical base of the educational system is not sufficiently developed, especially due to insufficient provision of modern information and communication tools. General socio-political, economic and spiritual cultural processes in our country are aimed at preserving independence, even though the laws on the education system and the decisions of the President and the Central Government were adopted, the introduction of modern information and communication tools in the field was not at the level of world requirements. With the arrival of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev at the head of our state, and the adoption of the Strategy of Actions in 2017, innovative changes began to take place in this field. On September 23, 2020, the new Law "On Education", the President's "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" (April 20, 2017), "On Measures to Further Improve the Information Technologies and Communications Sector" (February 19, 2018) , "On measures to increase the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" (June 5, 2018), "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" (October 8, 2019) more than 200 official documents were accepted. The pandemic that started in 2020 prompted the widespread use of distance learning methods in the education system, as in all fields. In essence, distance education is a technology of using modern information and communication tools, which serves to make the educational process, in any conditions, a continuous, sustainable reality. It was created as a technology to attract disabled people who returned to their country to social life and education, to provide them with various services during the Second World War, especially during the USA's aggression against Vietnam, and later it was fully implemented in correspondence education processes. It was necessary to occupy the disabled people who overwhelmed Europe with something, this situation encouraged

countries to create inclusive and distance education systems. Scientific and technical discoveries made by the 21st century have made inclusive and distance education a global reality, especially in the era of COVID 19, which caused a global crisis. The whole world has moved to distance education and distance services, which, in turn, has made modern information and communication tools a universal artefact. As a result, humanity has created new platforms, programs and modules for the use of scientific and technical discoveries. Today, no one knows what their number and size is in the global intercom, because every day hundreds, thousands, even millions of people enter the intercom, create their own sites, open Facebooks and expand the circle of communication. Although many countries are trying to monitor and control them, it is not known if any results have been achieved in this regard. The creation of a national interspace remains a challenge. But there are efforts to create a national interspace in the field of education and training under state and public control. For example, we can cite sites such as "Okibat", "Karindoshlar", "Sinfdozlar", "Choyxona" and "Kadrdonlar" in Telegram, which promote our national-spiritual and moral values against unethical screens in intermaterials, sites that create violence and aggressive mood. In addition, the effective use of modern information and communication technology allows some of our young people to create a national segment on the Internet. In his address to the youth of Uzbekistan, the President proudly mentioned that a group of young people led by Mekhrinoz Abbasova posted more than 10,000 Uzbek articles on Wikipedia[3].

Universal media space does not reject national features and capabilities, any information, standard and module can be placed in it. The Moodle platform coordinated with the above-mentioned Web and on-line mode is today being expressed in the system of higher education in Karakapogistan. This platform is "a special Web-oriented educational system that manages and streamlines the learning process and is designed for use on the Internet. Open source software is used to create the system. To use it, you need a database management program (My SGL or PostgreSGL), a PHP processor, a server configured with a Web service program (Apache IIS). As an operating system, you can use any of the popular systems (Windows. Linux, Mac OS X, Novwll Netware). At the time of writing the training module, the stable version of the system is mooble 2.5. The official website address of the system is: <http://www.mooble.org>. Mooble, abbreviated as Modular Object Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment, is a modular object-oriented dynamic learning environment (MOOBLE), a free web (web-oriented) application licensed under the GNU GPL license. The Mooble system is based on the "pedagogy of social constructivism"[4.25]. The Mooble platform is distributed in 160 countries of the world, in 72 languages, including the Uzbek language, through 37,000 versions. It is evident that the platform has the potential to combine universal and national resources. Candidate of philological sciences, associate professor J.Khoshniyazov, associate professor of philology, who is using these opportunities in Karakalpakstan, K. Samamutov, an employee of the Institute of Language and Literature named after N.Dawkaraev, leading researchers of the Karakalpak department of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan A.S.Muratov and E.Oteniyazov wrote scientific articles in the Karakalpak language. , we know that innovative developments and resources related to the ethnography of the country are being introduced to the Internet. The fact that the results of scientific research are published in foreign journals and through the Internet shows that Karakalpak ethnoculture and science are taking a place in the universal media space. In particular, with the help of "BFE Studio and Median Systeme" company, mass media and educational centers were computerized, the

editorial office of "Erkin Karakapakistan" newspaper, "Karakalpakstan" television, "Mawrit", "Dawir", "Karakalpakstan", "Assalawma aleykum Karakalpakstan!", The fact that "Diydar" TV programs are equipped with modern information and communication tools immediately attracted the attention of the audience[5.67-68]. If we look at these processes, we can see that the task of media centers is a priority in them. Communication takes place mainly among a narrow circle of intellectuals. Organization of communication with the masses, the general population, takes place in a traditional way, that is, in the subject-object style, left over from the Soviet era. Until 2016, in the activity of media centers, it was very weak to engage in live communication, to focus social opinion on current issues of the time. True, many articles and speeches were organized about the environmental situation in Karakalpakstan. For example, T.Qaipbergenov, A.Tajiev, I.Niyatullaev, O.Abdurakhmanov, K.Dauletmuratov, D.Allambergenov in "Erkin Karakalpakstan" newspaper and "Nokis haqiyqati" newspapers, "Aral", "Qaraqalpaqstan Muğallimi" magazines and "Qaraqalpaqstan" television. They paid attention to the current issues of the Karakalpak people and their life, and revealed the relevance of regional problems[6.72-74]. Nevertheless, the media centers did not have a wide range of communication, they even showed an adaptation to authoritarian rule. This situation is evident in our respondents' answers to the question "What topics do you think media centers should pay more attention to?".

The answers we received are divided as follows:

- 58 percent to "Economic problems"
- 53 percent to "Youth Employment"
- 51 percent to "Environmental problems"
- 44 percent to "Health"
- 32 percent to "Social and political issues"
- 31 percent to "Cultural household issues"
- 29 percent to "Moral education"
- 27 percent to "Education"
- 26 percent to "Issues of democracy and human rights"
- 21 percent to "The problems of women and girls"
- 17 percent to "Scientific problems"
- 11 percent to "Improvement of the environment"
- 4 percent to "International topics"

These answers can be expressed in the form of a diagram as follows.

Respondents indicate that socio-economic issues (58 percent), youth employment (53 percent) and ecology (51 percent) remain serious problems for the people of Karakalpakstan. The public around media centers, mainly journalists and academic staff, tend to organize communication around these problems. The main directions of their creative activity and materials in medicenters are related to socio-economic issues. At the same time, they have socio-political materials. Interest in topics related to democracy and human rights, education system, and health also occupy one of the leading positions. Especially in Karakalpak press and TV and radio programs, topics such as independence, spiritual heritage forgotten during the colonial period, the fate of the repressed, and the reflection of tragedies related to the island on the fate of people, give the national media space its uniqueness. They are published not only in national media centers, but also in intermaterials, international scientific journals and conference materials[7].

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